

STRUCTURAL EVALUATION OF MATERIALS USING FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS FOR EXOSKELETON 3D PRINTING

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Abstract - The brachial plexus, a network of nerves originating in the cervical spinal cord, controls limb movement and sensation. Neuropathies, caused by trauma, accidents, or tumors, can impair these functions, leading to pain, muscle weakness, and changes in sensitivity. Treatment typically includes painkillers, physiotherapy, and surgery, but these may not fully restore arm function. Exoskeletons have emerged as a potential solution, offering stability, strength amplification, and movement restoration. This study focuses on the development of a 3D-printed exoskeleton, comparing polylactic acid (PLA) and polyethylene glycol terephthalate (PETG) materials using Finite Element Analysis (FEA) to evaluate their structural performance.

Keywords - Brachial plexus, Exoskeleton, Finite Element Analysis (FEA), Neuropathies, Structural performance, 3D printing.

I. INTRODUÇÃO

A. Exoskeleton for Brachioradial Rehabilitation

The brachial plexus is a network of nerves that originate in the cervical spinal cord and reach the arm. It is responsible for controlling the movement of the limb and the sensations that the entire region can receive. However, neuropathies are diseases that can affect these functions, and they can be caused by a variety of reasons including direct trauma to the innervation, injuries from accidents or tumors. In general, the symptoms include pain, muscle weakness, loss of reflexes and changes in sensitivity which impact on the patient's quality of life [1].

Treatment for these diseases is conventional and usually includes painkillers to control pain, physiotherapy to strengthen the area and the possibility of surgery. However, these possibilities may not achieve complete restoration of the arm [1]. In this sense, exoskeletons have emerged as a solution. These robotic devices are designed to integrate with the human body, offering stability, amplifying strength and restoring lost movement. In general, they can be used both for patient rehabilitation and as assistive technology for everyday use in tasks that are not possible due to loss of movement.

This article is part of the development of an exoskeleton for assistive technology. It was modeled according to the ISO7250 standard: Basic human body measurements, in which a distance was sought between the arm and the device to place a foam.

The exoskeleton prototype in question has 4 parts to be made on the 3D printer and 3 parts to be made using Computer Numerical Control (CNC), but in this article, the focus will be on analyzing the polymeric materials. In Figure 1, parts 1,2,3,4 will be positioned on the arm, respectively on the proximal biceps, distal biceps, proximal forearm and distal forearm and attached to this limb with Velcro tape. These parts will be connected to each other by metal rods and the cycloidal reducer.

In this study, the distal biceps and proximal forearm parts were selected for finite element analysis (FEA) because the other polymeric parts are directly proportional to part 3, i.e. there was only a change in part size.

Figure 1: Exoeskeleton assembly.

B. PLA

The thermoplastic polymer, PLA, is often used in 3D printing, mainly because of its tensile strength and rigidity. Although its properties can be improved through changes in formulation or printing orientation, it is less resistant than other plastics such as acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS). Although it is difficult to manufacture complex parts, it has good

adhesion between layers and a low tendency to deform [2, 3].

The anisotropy, however, of PLA's mechanical properties, which result from the deposition characteristics during the printing process, presents challenges in predicting its performance, but these can be corrected by a theoretical model that takes into account the stress conditions on the failure surfaces. On the other hand, in view of its lightness, cost-effectiveness and ease of forming complex parts, PLA is considered a good material for making exoskeleton parts, as it reduces the weight of the device, manages to create parts that fit the human body and can be recycled as it is a material derived from renewable sources such as corn starch or sugar cane [2, 3].

C. PETG

Polyethylene terephthalate (PET), a thermoplastic polymer patented by John Rex Whinfield and James Tennant Dickson, proved its viability as a durable and versatile material for various industries. Later, an interaction between PET and cyclodimethanol (CHDM) led to the creation of PETG, which has: a higher glass transition temperature, less ability to crystallise with the application of heat, better heat resistance, high transparency and high ductility compared to PET. All these qualities give PETG a considerable tensile modulus and strength. However, this material can present increased internal tensions and possible ruptures. To improve tensile modulus and strength, PETG has been mixed with organic clay and polyglycolic acid [4].

The manufacturing techniques for this material vary from injection moulding, pressure moulding, 3D printing and thermoforming. Its main characteristics are that it is transparent and resistant to crystallisation when exposed to high levels of heat, as seen in the stamping process. PETG's photostability in the presence of ultraviolet radiation decreases as the CHDM content increases in the polymer structure. Thus, PETG can be reformed into an engineering-grade material using the distributed recycling process for manufacturing to be reused in various industrial projects. With these properties, the material is a candidate for making orthopaedic impressions [4].

D. Finite element analysis

Finite element analysis (FEA) was carried out to see the structural performance of the parts of the exoskeleton, mainly to find out about the safety factor, stress, displacement, deformations and reaction forces. This is essential to ensure that the design of the device is safe and effective for the patient, in such a way as to identify critical points where stresses are highest and ensure that the modeled structure is not compromised. In addition, FEA helps to bring credibility to the materials evaluated, which makes it easier to optimize the design before it is manufactured, such as reducing the amount of material in places that have little deformation [5].

II. OBJECTIVES

The aim of this article is to compare two materials (PLA and PETG) to be used in the 3D printing of exoskeleton parts. In the process, Finite Element Analysis was used in the Fusion

360 software to determine the structural performance and feasibility of the chosen materials in terms of safety, strength and durability. In this way, the comparison will make it possible to identify which material is most suitable for manufacturing the exoskeleton components, in such a way as to indicate the risk factor, stress, displacement, deformation and reaction forces in each part.

III. METHODS

First, the parts are modeled according to the geometric specifications of the ISO 7250 standard in the Fusion 360 software, ensuring accurate representation of human anthropometry. The materials are then characterized by their mechanical properties, including strength, rigidity, and deformation thresholds, to establish a realistic simulation environment [6].

Following this, the finite element simulation is set up to analyze the structural response under applied forces. For example, in the distal biceps component, as shown in Figure 2, forces related to the weights of the battery and motor are applied in the same direction on the upper part of the image, with magnitudes of 3N and 2N respectively, acting on the support that fixes them. Additionally, the weight of the metal rod (10N) and the pressure of the Velcro (1N) are incorporated into the analysis for a comprehensive evaluation. In Figure 3, the efforts of the Velcro acting on the proximal forearm part and the connection with the rod are represented. The restrictions include fixed conditions at the points where the parts will come into contact with the foam interacting with the human arm, replicating real operational constraints. This approach ensures the simulation captures both the functional and biomechanical aspects of the exoskeleton design.

Figure 2: Forces applied to the distal biceps part.

The simulation is run for both materials (PLA and PETG), using the same loading parameters and constraints. The results are recorded for later analysis, including safety factor, stresses, deformations, displacement and reaction forces. The analysis of the results compares the performance of the materials, identifying which material has the best strength and durability. In addition, the final weight of the part manufactured with each material is considered, given that lightness is an important factor for the comfort of the exoskeleton user.

Figure 3: Forces applied to the proximal forearm part.

Finally, the results are discussed, evaluating the advantages and disadvantages of each material for application in exoskeletons. The conclusion of this methodology will make it possible to determine which material, PETG or PLA, is more suitable for application in parts of this type of device, helping in the choice of the most appropriate material for production, taking into account both their mechanical properties.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For the PLA distal biceps piece, as shown in Figure 4, it showed a safety factor with good resistance to failure. The maximum stress is within the limits of the material and the displacement suggests a small deformation. The maximum deformation indicates adequate rigidity. In addition, each image shows the maximum and minimum values for each variable analyzed; these values are shown in Table 1. Finally, the reaction force indicated that the part is subject to light forces. Overall, PLA proved to be a suitable material for the application, with good safety and structural stability.

Figure 4: Simulation of the proximal part of the forearm in PETG: (a) Safety factor; (b) Stress; (c) Displacement; (d) Strain; (e) Reaction Force

The analysis of the PLA proximal forearm part, illustrated in Figure 5, indicated a very high factor of safety, which means a high resistance to failure. The stress was below the material's limit and the displacement was extremely low, suggesting that the part practically does not deform under load. The deformation indicated excellent rigidity. The reaction force shows that the part will cope well with light forces. So PLA also proved to be suitable for making this part. Additionally, the low levels of stress and minimal displacement imply that the PLA component will have a long service life under typical operational conditions, with minimal wear and tear. This makes PLA a reliable material choice, particularly in scenarios where precision and durability are crucial. The analysis confirms that PLA's performance meets the required standards for this application, ensuring both structural integrity and functional efficiency over time.

Figure 5: Simulation of the proximal part of the forearm in PLA: (a) Safety factor; (b) Stress; (c) Displacement; (d) Strain; (e) Reaction Force

The analysis of the PETG distal biceps piece in Figure 6 showed a slightly higher safety factor than PLA, indicating greater resistance to failure. The maximum stress was also higher than that of PLA, but still within safe limits. The maximum displacement suggests that PETG deforms slightly more than PLA. The maximum deformation indicates PETG's greater flexibility. In summary, PETG offers a slight advantage in strength and flexibility, making it a good alternative to PLA for this application.

Figure 6: Simulation of the proximal part of the forearm in PETG: (a) Safety factor; (b) Stress; (c) Displacement; (d) Strain; (e) Reaction Force

With the relevant values from the simulation and the limit values for each material, it was possible to make a numerical comparison of these results from Table 1 for the distal part of the biceps[7, 8].

Table 1: FEA results for distal biceps part

Distal biceps part					
	Min. Safety Factor	Max. Stress (MPa)	Max. Displacement (mm)	Max. Strain	Max. Reaction force (N)
PLA	6.312	7.842	0.006	0.003	0.110
PETG	6.861	8.016	0.009	0.005	0.117
Material Limits					
PLA	-	70.0	-	0.05	-
PETG	-	53.0	-	0.04	-

Comparing PETG and PLA in the distal biceps part, PETG stands out for being more resistant and flexible, which allows it to withstand slightly greater loads and deform more under pressure, making it a good choice for applications that require some malleability. On the other hand, PLA is more rigid and tends to deform less, which may be preferable in situations where structural rigidity is more important.

The simulation for the PETG proximal forearm part, in Fig-

ure 7, has a very high safety factor, minimal stress and deformation, and very little displacement. In short, the part is well within the limits of the material's strength and rigidity, offering safe and reliable operation.

Figure 7: Simulation of the proximal part of the forearm in PETG: (a) Safety factor; (b) Stress; (c) Displacement; (d) Strain; (e) Reaction Force

Similarly to the table for the distal biceps piece, Table 2 was assembled to visualize the minimum and maximum data for each of the parameters discussed for each of the materials.

Table 2: FEA results for proximal forearm part

Proximal forearm part					
	Min. Safety Factor	Max. Stress (MPa)	Max. Displacement (mm)	Max. Strain	Max. Reaction force (N)
PLA	15	0.014	1.160E-04	7.451E-06	0.508
PETG	15	0.014	1.850E-04	1.164E-05	0.482
Material Limits					
PLA	-	70.0	-	0.05	-
PETG	-	53.0	-	0.04	-

Although the maximum deformations and maximum displacements are small, the same conclusion can be drawn for the distal part of the biceps and the proximal part of the forearm. In this sense, the PLA's ability to deform less is a desirable feature, since it is expected that the device will not undergo many mechanical changes. In addition, the difference between the densities of PLA and PETG, 1.24 and 1.27 g/cm³ respectively, shows that the former will make a lighter part [9].

It's worth noting that the FEA simulation only took into account the static tension of the part, so it's worth carrying out other types of analysis such as thermal pressure and cooling of the electronics, since batteries and motors dissipate energy during their operation.

The results of this study present similarities and differences in relation to the materials that are common in exoskeletons. While metallic materials, such as aluminum alloys, are used due to their high strength, rigidity and low cost, they are heavier and may not meet all design needs, especially for devices that require precise and light movements, such as the EXOWRIST and RETRAINER-ARM exoskeletons. From another perspective, polymeric materials have been gaining ground due to their lightness, elasticity and ease of manufacture by 3D printing, as seen in devices such as ARMin III and ChARM, which use hybrid plastics to achieve high design complexity and better adaptation to patients' anthropometry. Thus, in this study, the choice of PLA and PETG reflects this trend, highlighting their suitability for rapid prototyping and structures that require moderate mechanical strength, low density and the ability to withstand deformation under light loads, in line with the search for efficient, low-cost solutions in the field of assistive devices [10, 11, 12].

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, both PLA and PETG proved to be suitable materials for manufacturing parts of the exoskeleton, each with specific characteristics that meet different project needs. PLA, with its rigidity and low deformation, is ideal for applications requiring a stable structure that is not susceptible to changes under load. PETG, on the other hand, with its greater resistance and flexibility, stands out in scenarios that require a more malleable material capable of withstanding greater loads without compromising the integrity of the part.

FEA showed that both materials offer a high safety factor and low stress in the parts evaluated, guaranteeing the reliability and safety of the exoskeleton. Although PETG offers a slight advantage in terms of strength and adaptability, PLA may be preferable in situations where lightness and rigidity are more valued.

REFERENCES

- [1] Z. Simmons. Electrodiagnosis of brachial plexopathies and proximal upper extremity neuropathies. *Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation Clinics of North America*, 24(1), 2012. Accessed on August 21, 2024, at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmr.2012.08.021>.
- [2] Y. Song, Y. Li, W. Song, K. Yee, K. Y. Lee, and V. L. Tagarielli. Measurements of the mechanical response of unidirectional 3d-printed pla. *Materials & Design*, 2017. Accessed on August 16, 2024, at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2017.03.051>.
- [3] L. Shi, P. Li, C. Liu, J. Zhu, T. Zhang, and G. Xiong. An improved tensile strength and failure mode prediction model of fdm 3d printing pla material: Theoretical and experimental investigations. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 2024. Accessed on August 16, 2024, at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobbe.2024.109389>.
- [4] C. Yan, C. Kleiner, A. Tabigue, V. Shah, G. Sacks, D. Shah, and V. DeStefano. Petg: Applications in modern medicine. *Engineered Regeneration*, 5(1):45–55, 2024. Accessed on August 14, 2024, at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engreg.2023.11.001>.
- [5] G. Nikhil, K. Ganesh, and M. Barman. Static structural analysis of lower extremity exoskeleton for industry working personnel using an analysis software. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 2023. Accessed on August 21, 2024, at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2023.06.457>.
- [6] International Organization for Standardization. Iso 7250: Basic human body measurements for technological design, 2017. 3rd ed., ISO, Geneva, Switzerland. Accessed on November 29, 2024, at: <https://www.iso.org/standard/65246.html>.
- [7] BCN3D. Technical data sheet pla, 2024. Accessed on October 4, 2024, at: https://www.bcn3d.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/BCN3D_FILAMENTS_TechnicalDataSheet_PLA_EN.pdf.
- [8] IEMAI. Petg technical data sheet (tds), 2024. Accessed on October 4, 2024, at: https://www.iemai3d.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/PETG_TDS_EN.pdf.
- [9] Bitfab. The densities of all 3d printing materials, 2024. Accessed on August 21, 2024, at: <https://bitfab.io/blog/3d-printing-materials-densities/>.
- [10] J. Cornejo. Mechatronic exoskeleton systems for supporting the biomechanics of shoulder-elbow-wrist: An innovative review. In *2021 IEEE International IOT, Electronics and Mechatronics Conference (IEMTRONICS)*, 2021. Accessed on November 29, 2024, at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/IEMTRONICS52119.2021.9422660>.
- [11] P. Santra, A. Mukhopadhyay, B. Debnath, M. A. Herbert, and S. Bhaumik. Active upper arm exoskeleton – design and kinematic analysis. In *2019 IEEE Region 10 Symposium (TENSYP)*, pages 462–467, 2019. Accessed on November 29, 2024, at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/TENSYP46218.2019.8971152>.
- [12] D. Huamanchahua, C. Castañeda-Vásquez, A. Vásquez-Espinoza, and A. Muñoz-Zevallos. Robotic devices types exoskeletons for elbow rehabilitation: A technological

review. In *2021 IEEE 12th Annual Ubiquitous Computing, Electronics & Mobile Communication Conference (UEMCON)*, pages 0791–0796, 2021. Accessed on

November 29, 2024, at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/UEMCON53757.2021.9666652>.